

A new testing approach for evaluating soil-reinforcement interaction in geosynthetic reinforced walls.

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Abstract

This study introduces an innovative apparatus designed to simulate soil-reinforced walls with geosynthetics, addressing challenges associated with reduced-scale models. The apparatus, featuring a box measuring 1.60 m x 1.10 m x 0.55 m with a glass face, replicates a segment of a geosynthetic-reinforced soil wall simulating the upper layer with an airbag. The methodology included assembling soil layers and geosynthetics, inflating a compressed air bag to apply pressure, and utilising displacement measuring devices (LVDTs) to monitor displacements at various wall heights. The findings validate the effectiveness of the apparatus in simulating soil-reinforced walls, offering a reliable and resource-efficient method for evaluating soil-geosynthetic interaction in a controlled environment.

Keywords chosen from the ICE Publishing list.

Soil-geosynthetic interaction; Reinforced soil; Testing, apparatus & methods.

1 Introduction

2 Geosynthetics have been recognised as a highly effective solution for geotechnical construction,
3 particularly for soil reinforcement. This preference stems from several advantages over traditional
4 structures, including economic benefits, easy installation processes, and a wide range of
5 materials and applications. These factors collectively provide geosynthetics a versatile option in
6 geotechnical engineering. The functioning of this material consists of reducing the soil shear
7 stress and redistributing this tension in the soil, resulting in internal confinement. This interaction
8 between soil reinforcement has been studied by many authors (Abu-Farsakh *et al.*, 2019; Barajas
9 *et al.*, 2024; Bathurst *et al.*, 2000; Elton and Patawaran, 2004; Guler *et al.*, 2007; Ho and Rowe,
10 1996; Holtz *et al.*, 2002; Kerry Rowe, 2001; Pham, 2009; Wu and Pham, 2013; Yang *et al.*, 2014).

11
12 In this context, the assessment of vertical spacing has gained significant attention in studies
13 investigating this interaction, employing methods such as numerical simulation (Abu-Farsakh *et al.*
14 *et al.*, 2019; Guler *et al.*, 2007; Ho and Rowe, 1996; Holtz *et al.*, 2002; Kerry Rowe, 2001) or physical
15 modelling (Barajas *et al.*, 2024; Bathurst *et al.*, 2000; Elton and Patawaran, 2004; Wu and Pham,
16 2013; Yang *et al.*, 2014). Within physical modelling, several techniques are available to represent
17 structures. Large-scale models are seldom used due to the challenges they present in terms of
18 control, as well as the considerable time, material, and financial resources required for their
19 execution (Jha *et al.*, 2005). Conversely, reduced-scale models have gained popularity in
20 academia due to their cost-effectiveness and ease of manipulation. Another widely used approach
21 involves models subjected to varied gravity conditions ($g \neq 1$) in centrifuge testing, which is
22 commonly employed to simulate and study structural behaviour under different scaling conditions.

23
24 In reduced-scale models, achieving similarity between soil and geosynthetics requires careful
25 attention to the interface mechanism. As the soil deforms, the reinforcement must deform
26 correspondingly. This alignment is particularly crucial because directly scaling a model often
27 results in inconsistencies, especially concerning soil granulometry. For example, these
28 inconsistencies in soils composed of sand stem from the material's dilatancy and its complex
29 stress-strain behaviour (Barajas *et al.*, 2024). These requirements, governed by the π
30 Buckingham-Vaschy, principles, provide analytical solutions to express physical phenomena.

31 They rely on relationships involving specific dimensionless numbers that are independent of one
32 another (Jha *et al.*, 2005).

33

34 An alternative to addressing this challenge is to conduct tests using centrifuge simulation, a
35 technique that ensures scale consistency over time. However, the construction and operation of
36 a centrifuge require advanced infrastructure and specialized equipment, which are not readily
37 available in all academic institutions. Given these constraints, the study of vertical spacing in soil
38 reinforcement remains a critical yet somewhat ambiguous area of research. Many authors have
39 turned to reduced-scale or real-scale physical modelling using the available resources to gain
40 insights into the underlying mechanisms, as demonstrated in Table 1.

41

42 Given that real-scale devices entail considerable investments of time, financial, and material
43 resources, a smaller-scale apparatus, enabling the utilisation of materials more closely
44 resembling real-world conditions and less susceptible to the scale effect, proves highly
45 advantageous. This paper presents a new testing approach to assess the interaction between
46 soil and reinforcement, addressing challenges encountered in representations at reduced and
47 field scales. The key concept involves replicating a segment of a wall constructed from soil
48 reinforced with geosynthetics to simulate the upper layer artificially. By representing a section,
49 this approach enables the use of materials more closely related to those employed in actual field
50 scenarios, thereby mitigating issues associated with scale effects.

51

52 **Table 1. Geosynthetic tests in reduced or natural scale**

53

Reference	Test type	Dimension L (m) x W (m) x H (m)	Soil	Geotextile	Measurement sensor
Mehrjardi et al. (2019)	Plate load	1.2 x 0.7 x 0.7	Sand (d ₅₀ 3mm) Gravel (d ₅₀ 6mm) Gravel (d ₅₀ 12mm) Gravel (d ₅₀ 16mm)	Geocell	Dial gauge
Barajas et al. (2024)	Pullout	1.5 x 0.7 x 0.48	Tropical soil Clayey sand	Geogrid	LVDT and Tell-Tales

Wu et al. (2008)	Vertical load	7.34 x 5.75 x 4.65	Silty sand	Woven geotextile	LVDT, displacement potentiometer, strain gauge and contact pressure cell.
Morsy et al. (2019)	Pullout	1.5 x 0.75 x 1.20	Washed pea gravel	Woven geotextile	Camera, lateral earth pressure and displacement sensors.
Moghaddas Tafreshi et al. (2023)	Plate load	2.20 x 2.20 x 0.75	Well-graded sand	Geocell	LVDT

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55

56 2. Experimental program

57 This study aims to evaluate the results of reduced-scale model tests using an apparatus devised
58 to simulate geosynthetic-reinforced soil walls (GRSW). The primary goal is to replicate a part of
59 a prototype GRSW at a reduced scale so that particle size effects on the results are negligible.

60

61 The initial test was performed with a low stiffness/strength geosynthetic material intending to
62 simulate the model at a condition close to the ultimate state. The prototype was considered to
63 have a total height of 3.80 m and reinforcement vertical spacing of 0.15 m. Therefore, the GRSW
64 model, which represents a slice of the prototype, was constructed with six layers of compacted
65 sand with 0.15 m-thickness, which results in a model height (prototype slice) of 0.9 m.

66

67 To simulate the weight of the upper part of the GRSW prototype on the model, a vertical surcharge
68 of 40 kPa was applied to the top layer of the model, which corresponds to a geostatic stress of a
69 soil portion with 2.60 m height. Figure 1 illustrates the idealized model.

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71

72 **Figure 1. Simulated layer configuration**

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74 **2.1. Apparatus**

75 Figure 2 shows a schematic layout of the testing box constructed for this study. Due to its scaling
 76 scale between 1:3 and 1:5 (ratio of the model to prototype dimensions), the modelling with this
 77 apparatus benefits from the possibility of using materials more closely resembling those used in
 78 the practice. Moreover, the use of a reduced-scale model enables a reduced time for model
 79 preparation and demands a lower financial investment as well as less material.

80

81 The box structure consists of 4 steel frames (L-section steel beams) braced over the length of the
 82 box by L-section steel beams at each corner of the frames. The wall panels are made of 25 mm-
 83 marine plywood on 4 sides of the box (base, back, top, and one lateral side). The other lateral
 84 side of the box, divided into 3 panels, is divided into three panels, each covered with 10 mm thick
 85 tempered glass sheets. This setup allows for lateral observation of the model and enables
 86 monitoring of grain displacement through imaging in future tests, as illustrated in Figure 2a,
 87 however, no images were captured for this research. The front of the apparatus is open to enable
 88 the adaptability to various types of GRSW facings such as blocks or geosynthetic-wrapped faces,
 89 as shown in Figure 2b. Additionally, the open front face facilitates the attachment and movement
 90 of wooden plates that assist in constructing the wall layers and facilitate displacement
 91 measurements by granting the secure attachment of measurement devices.

92

93 The configuration of the apparatus involves applying two sheets of Mylar sheets (commercially
 94 known as space blanket) to the lateral plywood panels to reduce friction between the soil and side
 95 walls (Morsy *et al.*, 2019). On the base of the box, a 5 mm-thick EVA (Ethylene Vinyl Acetate)
 96 sheet was placed in contact with the marine plywood. Above this EVA sheet, the soil and
 97 geosynthetic layers are arranged. Another EVA sheet is positioned between the top layer of soil
 98 and the compressed air bag, as illustrated in Figure 2c. The use of EVA sheets aims to provide a
 99 stiffness (flexibility) comparable to the soil and thus mimic the vertical displacement of the soil
 100 layers above and below the zone of the GRSW simulated by the model.
 101

102

103 **Figure 2. Schematic layout of the testing box: (a) side view of the developed apparatus; (b)**
 104 **front view of the apparatus; (c) longitudinal section of the apparatus configuration.**
 105

106 **2.2. Soil model**

107 The soil model used is a fine silica sand composed of subangular particles with 90% of particles
108 smaller than 1.11 mm, 50% smaller than 0.67 mm (D50 - average grain size), 40% smaller than
109 0.52 mm, and 10% smaller than 0.21 mm (Figure 3). The minimum dry density is $\rho_{min}= 1.44$
110 g/cm^3 and the maximum dry density is $\rho_{max}= 1.62 g/cm^3$. The soil model was dynamically
111 compacted inside the box aiming to provide an average dry density of $\rho_d = 1.56 g/cm^3$ (a relative
112 density, DR, of ~70%).

113

114

115 **Figure 3. Sand particle size.**

116

117 **2.3. Measurement devices**

118 The measurements in this study focused on face wall displacements mainly at three points over
119 the model height using Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) coupled to a data logger.
120 The data logger is manufactured by Wykeham Farrance and is capable of recording
121 displacement, pressure, and load data, in a resolution of 0.001 unities. Three LVDT devices were
122 used, each with different measuring capacities: 100 mm, 50 mm, and 25 mm, labelled Displ100,
123 Displ50, and Displ25. Additionally, the data acquisition system is equipped with data collection
124 software, which facilitates the acquisition of results in a text file format (.txt) and enables real-time
125 visualization of the displacement-time response.

126

127 The vertical stress was applied to the model's top surface using an airbag (dunnage bag) inflated
128 by an 830 kPa-capacity air compressor. The air pressure was monitored with a digital manometer
129 (1800 kPa capacity and 1 kPa resolution) incorporated into the system.

130

131 **2.4. Physical models**

132 Physical modelling can be divided into two main stages: the model construction sequence and
133 the model loading.

134

- 135 • Construction procedure:

136 The initial step involved applying a space blanket to the box side walls, which were positioned
137 to prevent friction between sand and box walls. Subsequently, the EVA sheet was placed at
138 the base of the box to simulate the vertical displacement of the lower layers of the prototype
139 which were not considered in the model. The space blanket was also placed over the bottom
140 EVA sheet at the initial 80 cm from the model front face, to allow the soil to slide completely
141 in this contact, enabling the soil failure wedge to move freely in the horizontal direction. A
142 wood plate was affixed to the front face of the box to serve as a guide so that the face of each
143 layer of soil did not move during compaction. The sand was compacted dynamically to
144 achieve the target relative density (DR) of ~70%. Figure 4a illustrates the last construction
145 stage after removing the wood plate facing. The wood plate was removed upon completing
146 the construction of layers, subsequently, another EVA sheet and the loading airbag were
147 placed on the top sand layer.

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Figure 4. (a) Side view of the physical model; (b) LVDT device placement on the wall face.

153

A specific connecting device had to be attached to the air inlet of the airbag for inflation purposes. This filling apparatus included a manometer positioned in a series configuration to regulate the pressure within the airbag from the air compressor. After these adjustments, the displacement measuring devices (LVDTs) were finally positioned in front of the wall, as shown in Figure 4b. Displ100 was positioned at the top of the wall face, followed by Displ50 and Displ25. The numbering of each measuring device corresponds to its measurement range. Subsequently, these devices were coupled to the data acquisition device.

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- Model loading:

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Initially, the bag was filled to 40 kPa, with the pressure sustained for 10 minutes.

163

Subsequently, the bag was deflated and refilled, repeated 14 times. The repetition of this

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process was determined based on observations from the pilot test, which revealed that the

165

displacement begins to stabilize near the 14th cycle.

166

167 **3. Results**

168 Figure 5a presents the displacements over the 14 cycles with the vertical surcharge increasing
169 from zero to 40 kPa and then decreasing to zero again. Displ25 was placed at the base of the
170 wall, precisely at layer No. 2, Displ50 was positioned at mid-height, specifically at layer No. 4, and
171 Displ100 was located at the top of the wall, at layer No. 5. In the first cycle, the face horizontal
172 displacement was 2.3 mm at the model top, while in the mid-height it was 1.28 mm (Figure 5b).
173 At the model base, some displacement was only observed in the second cycle. In soil-reinforced
174 walls, displacements near the base are anticipated to be smaller than at the top due to the
175 formation and rotation of the failure wedge. Nevertheless, the horizontal movement of the model
176 base may also have been influenced by some non-negligible friction with the EVA sheet, even
177 though anti-friction measures were taken (as described in subsection 2.4). Moreover, since the
178 soil model was prepared via dynamic compaction, the lower layers may have experienced
179 increased grain accommodation, which results in greater density and stiffness in comparison with
180 the upper layers.

181
182 During the model construction, an initial settling of the grains and face movement was observed
183 upon removing the face support (wood plate) used to construct the layers. This settling resulted
184 in a movement of the model front face that could not be registered by the LVTDs, which had not
185 yet been installed during the model construction phase. Moreover, the underlying layers
186 experienced grain accommodation during the model construction because the face support was
187 removed when an overburden of at least one layer was above. As a result, the bottom layers are
188 under pressure with their front faces free to move, allowing for grain accommodation throughout
189 most of the process. This accommodation process did not occur in the upper layers because there
190 was no soil overburden when the face support was removed, and the airbag had not yet been
191 inflated. Consequently, the initial deformation was smaller in the upper layers.

192
193 Figure 5a also shows that the face horizontal displacement decreased with the cycles. While the
194 increase in permanent horizontal displacement ($\Delta U_{h, perm}$) at the top was 2.15 mm in the first cycle,
195 in the last (14th) cycle it was 0.23 mm, corresponding to 11% of the value of the first cycle. The

196 most significant displacement occurred in the first three cycles (50% of the total face horizontal
 197 movement occurred within this period), which can be attributed to grain accommodation.
 198

199

200 **Figure 5. (a) Cumulative displacements over the total number of cycles; (b) Displacement**
 201 **in the first cycle.**
 202

203 Figure 6a compares the total and permanent displacements of the model face normalised by the
 204 prototype height (3.8 m). This figure shows that almost the majority of total displacements are
 205 permanent. Moreover, the trend of displacement increases fits with a log or a power-law function,
 206 with an indication of stabilisation in the displacement rate. Figure 6b shows that after the 12th
 207 cycle, the displacement rate shows a nearly constant value, which corroborates the trend in
 208 stabilisation in the displacement rate.

209

210

211 **Figure 6. (a) total and permanent relative horizontal displacement of the model face with**
 212 **cycles; (b) increase rate of total and permanent horizontal displacements of the model**
 213 **face.**
 214

215 The displacement registered at the three points of the model face (heights of 14%, 22%, and 26%
 216 of the prototype height, H) was used to estimate the overall horizontal movement of the prototype
 217 wall, which was based on the LVDT measurements and the total height of the prototype. The use
 218 of a log-normal fit provided reasonable estimations for the prototype wall movement. Figure 7a
 219 presents the experimental data plotted with the prototype height as well as the log fit for the first
 220 and the last cycle (14th). The maximum horizontal displacement estimated for the first cycle was
 221 0.19% H , and for the last cycle was 0.66% H . These values of horizontal displacements lie in the
 222 range usually observed in the field for GRSW (from 0.2% to 1.2%). In addition, a linear expression
 223 was fitted to the experimental data (Figure 7b). The maximum horizontal displacement estimated
 224 for the first cycle with the linear fit was 0.42% H , while for the last cycle it was 1.42% H . Although
 225 these values are slightly higher than those reported in the literature for the service condition, they

226 are still lower than some field observations, such as those reported by Crouse and Wu (2003),
 227 where deformations of up to 1.5% were observed.
 228

229
 230 **Figure 7. Extrapolation of horizontal wall displacements to the prototype; (a) Linear trend;**
 231 **(b) trend using straight line equation.**
 232

233 Drawing from the closely aligned behaviour with real-scale observations, it can be affirmed that,
 234 unlike the findings of Mehrjardi et al. (2019) who faced scale effects due to a smaller apparatus,
 235 the magnitude of displacements for the current of tests was comparable to full-scale observations.
 236

237 **4. Conclusions**

238 This study presented an experimental investigation using a testing apparatus constructed to
 239 simulate prototype structures of geosynthetics-reinforced soil walls with a small scale of reduction,
 240 ensuring that the geostatic stresses and the mechanical response of the soil in the model to be
 241 in similarity to those in the prototype. To evaluate the suitability of this apparatus, a modelling of

242 a geosynthetic-reinforced wall with a 15 cm layer height was conducted. The findings are outlined
243 below:

244

- 245 – The performance of the soil, geosynthetic, and overall arrangement exhibited similarities
246 to a real structure in service condition. Higher displacements were observed at the top of
247 the model, which is comparable to a full-scale GRSW.
- 248 – The maximum horizontal displacements of the model face ranged from 0.19%H in the
249 first cycle to 0.26%H in the last cycle. A greater rate of displacement increase was
250 observed in the first two cycles. After six cycles, the displacement accumulation tended
251 to show a stabilized rate.
- 252 – The extrapolation of the horizontal displacement at the top of the wall based on the
253 displacements obtained with the physical model can be an approach to be used in the
254 prediction of the performance of GRSW under cyclic loads.

255

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259

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